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PACIFICUS

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- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“LIFE STANDARD”

The standard of life is composed of quantifiable ingredients of happiness, and sorrowness constructed by love with the intention to serve the desires of every soul. The following poems formed into poetry are products of imaginations and inspirations, criticisms and even real encounters, that showers moral lessons through the real-life experience of two lovers, two or more minds.

Laughter from a Demon

Things were so beautiful before,
I was unleashed with your comforting fervor
I never knew
You're just an element of crabbing skin that allure

Never had passed in my wicked mind,
You build me high, so that you can crack me while I fly
I was just appreciating the moment
Innocent, plain and pure, what an intricate pigment

More and more, I found the key beyond the boundaries
It leads me a map, so beautiful but I pass the cemeteries
Then I stand there, I took a book, telling stains in a mattress
More and more I understand you're just a fake fortress

With the favor of the odds,
You never get me with a full blood
Murder me not twice, u understand, I will be wise
All I can say, you never did it, now listen at you're back
You will simply hear me,
Hear me from a laugh of a demon.

The Brainless Mouth

We smile, glance to each and others
The mouth curves, we're siblings
From different mothers

We talk and share for hours
The connection strengthens,
We represent special ores

We wave and say hi sweetly
We realized the respect, we're so friendly

I walked and never noticed you
Without any intentions,
I was just busy not seeing you

We walk and talk differently
We have our own busyness, s
till we're friends apparently

A month passed, limelight poured my way
I saw you there, I say hi, you waved back,
Without say

Everything renowned the spotlight
I never changed; I say hi, you say "why?"

Months passed again
I never saw you, I try to regain

Once for a while, o opened my news feed
You statted something, I cant get rid

I never understand what I did to you
We're not that close, but I mean something to you

Then I realize how the crabs pull others down
You do it to others, laughing like a clown

You brag your mouth and talk to the public
Telling stories, lies and lies, cryptic

You drag may soul down, lower and brown
As lower as you can, like the colors in your town

I can't even imagine how you were able to say those

I thought you were true, unlike my way to foes

Anyways I realized, its part of your system
You're like a palengkero, or should I say
Palengkero in dim
Using your tiny brain thru your brainless mouth

Beautiful Lie

I wonder
How magical it is
I look a breath, you're on that side
I took a blink, you're on my side

I put it into an eye
Now I'm holding your hand and I
I just asked you before
But now I'm asking for more

Things go down, all the words reverse
I look at you, full of impressions
Lie beneath your feet
Like a blue print lying for a tampered beat

The scar travelled, scarred me all over
I build all my defenses, just to recover my fences
Now look how you crashed it down,
I rebuild the castle without any frown

Now things reverse, all you did inverse
Follow my shadow; you will end up holding a hallow
You will never get it back; I'm on a subway of taking it back
Feels great I'm controlling the castle
Go with your back

Now you shall cry in double,
Eat your pride fictitious like parable
Act like an idiot, hammered with a horrible table
You will never get it, I'm done, get it?

Anyways, I'm happy with your effort
But I'm happier to laugh at your effort
The world is new now, and I will rule now
You're just a past, my former.
My yesterday, my sarcastic lie,
Say hello my former.

Standard, I am

I have a friend whom you may know
He looks at the top of mountain
Saying
There I will go

I have a friend whom you would know
He likes to play games
Wishing
He will win and flow

I have a friend people always knew
He played games
Acting
He dominates and throw

I have a friend slowly I never knew
He almost lost a grip
Tampering
Things he doesn't I want to do
I have a friend I pulled and let him go
He brained thrice
Stopped
And gained himself, true as he goes

I have a friend tampered by pressure
He understood himself
Gained
And says I am standard, planed.

Pins in the Pageant

The people clap at you
They say you're awesome
I'll say it isn't awesome

All they see is the smile and that walk
Panelists judge you
I'll say it isn't easy to be

When that moment, you wind the crowd
You kill the other's clock
I'll say it isn't that tack

You wear those standard covers
You great that aura

I'll say the pin cuts inside

The middle stage gives you spotlight
You flaunt yourself
At the backstage, you're wearing pins.

The Mirage

We live in the world where all we see
I what we see
We live there
And then, we leave there

You see the world through your window
You see the caption
You front it
And then, they front you

I live in the world where all I do is do
Created the mirage
So true to it
And they, they judge you

We should see the world clear as it is
Preferring fabulous
Pure to it
And we, we stain it

We are not as clear as the world
We create illusion
Imagine it
And you, you're just a mirage, die now.

Your Parfum. . .

Remember those days when we're together
just a glimpse from your windows
I reached the climax of serenity

Just as I walk with you palms fitted to mine
I savor the moment just as how everything pauses
It will take us five seconds to complete a blink of an eye

I can still cleanly recall that cottony plum
I kiss every night when I say goodnight
And those eyes who summoned into me a spell

But now I linger with this moment in time
As we take the seconds which draw us miles from each other
Only the smell in your parfum will remind me of the pain I suffer

You're so enough and too much for me
You're so good and beautiful
You, you are, you're everything, you parfum, it lingers

